

Sleep Disorders in Children with ASD: An ABA-Oriented Intervention

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Abstract

Sleep disturbances are very common in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and have a profound impact on their neurological development and daily functioning. Sleep disruption contributes to difficulties in falling asleep, staying asleep, and overall sleep quality, and sensory processing difficulties can further exacerbate these disturbances, affecting arousal regulation and environmental responsiveness during sleep. A key consequence of these mechanisms is that sleep disturbances are learned and, as such, can be unlearned with appropriate ABA-oriented strategies that have been shown to be effective in treating sleep disturbances in children with autism. Based on this assumption, the authors of this study implemented a treatment programme by identifying the environmental factors that negatively affected the sleep of children with ASD.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Sleep Disorders, Circadian Rhythm, Treatment of Sleep Disorders in ASD.

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Introduction

Sleep performs various functions, such as promoting brain development, consolidating memory and learning, promoting growth hormone secretion, strengthening the immune system and allowing the brain to “clean itself” of waste toxins produced during wakefulness. It is therefore very important that children sleep for as long as they need to, avoiding waking them arbitrarily and allowing them to regulate their own waking times [1]. In fact, sleep patterns change as children grow: from 16-17 hours of sleep in the first week of life, to 15 hours at around 6 months, then 14 hours at around 1 year, 13 hours at around 2 years, 12 hours at around 3 years, 11 hours after 6 years, 9 hours after 10 years, and 8 hours in adolescence. In addition, REM (Rapid Eye Movement) sleep, during which most dreams occur and which is crucial for memory consolidation and cognitive recovery, is more extensive in very young children because it is functional for brain development and decreases by about 14% in adults [2].

The alternation of different sleep cycles generally leads young children to micro-awakenings between cycles and, as their sleep cycles are shorter, this means that they wake up more frequently: in fact, assuming 6 hours of sleep, an adult may wake up 3 times compared to 6 times for a newborn. So, what often happens is that micro-awakenings occur between sleep cycles. Young children usually find it difficult to fall back asleep on their own between cycles and therefore call for adults to comfort them. This is normal, but there are times when the incidence of night-time awakenings between sleep cycles increases: these are the

so-called “sleep regression” phases; for example, when the child learns to move independently (crawling and walking) and in the period up to 18 months/2 years of age when separation anxiety is very present and therefore even separating to go to sleep is a problem for young children. Other possible causes of waking up are: teething, inadequate nutrition (digestibility, abundance, etc.), sensitivity to noise, starting nursery or preschool, the birth of a little brother or sister, family tensions, changes in daily routines and, especially today, excessive exposure to electromagnetic emissions (cordless phones, mobile phones, tablets, TVs, wireless, etc.), to name a few [3].

The consequences of insufficient or poor-quality sleep in children are manifold and can lead to various disorders, including: reduced school performance and learning problems, drowsiness, cognitive difficulties (inattention, poor concentration, memory deficits, etc.), emotional dysregulation, risk of accidental trauma, obesity, counter-control and depressive disorders. In addition, a child's sleep problems can have repercussions on the whole family, contributing to the development of maternal depression and significant family stress [4].

So what can be done to prevent children from waking up at night and improve their sleep? Are there any methods or procedures to regulate it?

When children cannot fall asleep or wake up during the night, the following strategies can be used to make bedtime easier for both them and their parents [5]:

- *Stick to a bedtime routine every night.* Get your child used to falling asleep at the same time from an early age, adapting the family's routine

to that of the child and not vice versa, establishing and maintaining the same bedtime rituals.

- *Always have your child sleep in the same environment* (their own bedroom or, in the first few months, in their parents' bedroom) that is properly prepared, with soft, warm lighting and no electronic devices (TV, computer, tablet, etc.) turned on, and possibly with soft, monotonous music playing in the background.

- *Avoid letting children sleep in their parents' bed.* Getting children used to independence also means letting them sleep in their own environment and, if they wake up during the night, always putting them back in their own bed.

- *Never use tablets or other electronic devices after dinner.* Switch everything off at least an hour before bedtime. The light from these devices reduces the production of melatonin, which promotes sleep.

- *Avoid stimulants after 4 p.m.* Do not give your child caffeinated drinks (tea, cola, etc.) or chocolate.

- *Do not give your child too much food or water before bedtime.* Avoid milk or other liquids, including chamomile tea, when your child wakes up. Instead, use a comforting object to help them fall back asleep (e.g., a dummy).

- *Separate feeding from sleep.* In the first few months of life, as soon as you notice that your baby is no longer sucking strongly and is closing their eyes, take them off the breast and put them in their cot.

- *Stick to a regular feeding schedule during the day.* Even if your baby goes to nursery, try to keep the same times for lunch, snacks and dinner, adapting your schedule to theirs.

- *Promote a balanced diet.* Choose foods containing fibre (green vegetables, legumes and cereals), white meat and oily fish; all foods that contain tryptophan, an amino acid that is a precursor to melatonin.

But what happens in children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)?

Sleep disorders in children with ASD

Sleep disorders in children with autism are very common and are a common concern for many families: most children end up sleeping in their parents' bed and sleep problems often persist over time. These disorders, with an estimated prevalence of 40% to 80%, include insomnia (20-30%; difficulty falling asleep or staying asleep, with many people taking longer to fall asleep and waking up frequently during the night), parasomnias (25%; abnormal behaviours that occur during sleep, such as muscle contractions or unusual movements), circadian rhythm disorders (7%; problems with the body's internal clock, which can disrupt sleep-wake cycles), respiratory disorders and sleep apnoea (2-3%; structural abnormalities of the upper airways, which can cause repeated interruptions and resumptions of breathing during sleep), sleep-related movement disorders (1-2%; restless legs syndrome, periodic limb movements, REM sleep behaviour disorder and bruxism, characterised by involuntary movements, jerks or teeth grinding during rest) and hypersomnia (0.01-0.20%; sleep disorders characterised by excessive daytime sleepiness, even when getting enough sleep at night) that can aggravate the main symptoms of ASD and negatively affect the quality of life of both the individual and their family [6-8].

However, before implementing a behavioural sleep programme, it is important to rule out any medical causes (respiratory and cardiovascular problems, pain, gastroesophageal reflux, etc.) that may be causing the disorder. If sleep problems are believed to be behavioural in nature, the first step is to have caregivers complete a sleep diary or undergo a semi-structured interview (Fig. 1) to determine the extent of the problem and potential environmental factors that could negatively affect the child's sleep. Baseline data collection should continue until a consistent sleep pattern (or lack thereof) or dysfunctional behaviour is identified, and this information can then be used to evaluate the effectiveness of sleep intervention. The baseline, through the diary or interview, should reveal:

the time the child goes to bed, the behaviours the child engages in before going to bed, situations that occur at home while the child is in bed that could affect their sleep, activities the child engages in before falling asleep, the time the child wakes up during the night and in the morning, and whether the child sleeps during the day; based on the results collected, various interventions can be considered [9,10].

Manipulating bedtime routines does not always result in effective treatment of sleep disorders, making further intervention necessary. The choice of procedure depends largely on when the sleep disorders occur. Below are some strategies that may be useful in improving the sleep behaviour of children with autism:

Escape Extinction

Escape extinction is an intervention that involves preventing or removing access to the reinforcement that previously maintained the behaviour. During this procedure, the parent implements the night-time sleep routine that culminates in putting the child to bed and leaving the room. Each time the child wakes up and attempts to leave the room, the parent returns them to bed with minimal discussion and interaction. This procedure should be repeated until the child remains in their bed and falls asleep [11,12]. If the child exhibits serious behavioural problems (self-harm, climbing on furniture, etc.), the parent should remain in the room to monitor the child's safety with minimal interaction, also considering the use of a video surveillance system to monitor the situation from another room.

Graduated Escape Extinction

When it is not possible to use an escape extinction procedure, the parent can implement a graduated extinction intervention. This treatment procedure should be used when the child has difficulty falling asleep, wakes up frequently during the night, and exhibits night-time anger behaviours. Similar to the escape extinction procedure, a graded procedure begins by putting the child to bed and leaving the room [10]. When crying or angry behaviour occurs, the parent will wait for a predetermined period of time before returning to the child's room. The latency of this response will increase systematically until the child falls back asleep before the parent enters [13].

Shifting Bedtime with Response Cost

This procedure first involves determining the actual time the child falls asleep once put to bed and adding an additional 30 minutes to the next bedtime. For example, if the child is put to bed at 8:30 p.m. and falls asleep at 9:00 p.m., the assigned bedtime would now be moved to 9:00 p.m. Once the time is set, it is important that the child be kept awake until 9:00 p.m. to increase the likelihood that they will be tired at the established bedtime. If the child falls asleep within 15 minutes of being put to bed, the bedtime should be moved back by reducing the time by 30 minutes the following night (the 9:30 p.m. bedtime is reduced to 9:00 p.m.). If the child does not fall asleep within 15 minutes of being put to bed, they will be taken out of bed for approximately 15 minutes. During this time, the child will not be encouraged to fall asleep nor should they be engaged in stimulating activities. The aim is to increase their motivation to sleep. At the end of the 15-minute interval, the child will be put back to bed. This procedure will be repeated until the child falls asleep. Bedtime will then be postponed by 30 minutes the following evening (increased from 8:30 p.m. to 9:00 p.m.). This cycle should be repeated until the child falls asleep at the time set by the parents [14].

Scheduled Awakenings

The "scheduled awakenings" procedure involves waking the child (by gently touching them or speaking softly to them) approximately 30 minutes before the most frequent night-time awakenings identified previously. Once the child is awake, the parent allows them to fall back asleep. The plan is repeated every night until the child is able to sleep through the night for 5-7 consecutive days. Once this criterion has been

met, one night of waking up per week can be skipped until the child no longer wakes up during the night [11].

The Bedtime Pass

If the child resists falling asleep in order to call or leave the bedroom to look for their parents, they may be given a pass (a small card with the child's name written at the top), issued by the parents, which can be exchanged for leaving the bedroom for a short period of time and for a specific purpose: to have a drink, go to the toilet or hug their parent. Once the pass has been used, the child must return it to the parent until the next bedtime. Depending on how often the child calls or leaves the room (as identified during the baseline), the child may be given additional passes. If the child exhibits problematic sleep behaviours after exchanging passes, the parent should use the escape extinction procedure [15-17].

Method

Participant

David is a child of about 6 years of age with Autism Spectrum Disorder (Level 2: DSM-V), who, at the time of admission about a year ago, had difficulty falling asleep and woke up during the night exhibiting disruptive

behaviours (whining, jumping on the bed, playing, throwing objects, etc.), forcing his parents to spend entire nights awake. During the initial phase, the parents were asked to answer the questions in the interview in Fig. 1, which did not reveal any particular medical problems, but did reveal environmental (afternoon naps, use of electronic devices, altered bedtime rituals) and situational problems (change in bedtime, separation anxiety, difficulty falling back asleep after waking up) related to bedtime and night-time awakenings [18]. Therefore, it was suggested to measure the child's sleep onset time and frequency of night-time awakenings, but the unreliability of the data due to the emotional and physical collapse of the parents, who were unable to wake up to take the measurements, led the authors of this study to use a smartwatch, worn by the child, to monitor his sleep. This device was accompanied by a smartphone application used to provide a record of the various stages of sleep. Despite the low accuracy of the measurement and the low reliability of its ability to accurately report sleep parameters (REM and NON-REM stages), it still allowed the child's movements coinciding with awakenings to be detected using an accelerometer [19]. This measurement (the baseline) shows that the child wakes up 4-5 times during the night (Fig. 1).

INTERVIEW ABOUT SLEEP		
Name:	Age:	Interviewee:
Interviewer:	Date:	
Instructions: Interview the carers of the child who has difficulty falling asleep and answer the questions by placing an X in the "YES" (Y) or "NO" (N) boxes. For each "YES" answer, write a qualifying comment in the line below the question or, if the answer is long, on a separate sheet of paper, specifying the question number.		
	Factors	A
Medical factors	1. Did your child's difficulty falling asleep appear during a particular season? <i>If YES, which one?</i>	Y N
	2. Did the difficulty coincide with psychological distress? (Anxiety, meltdowns, fears, etc.) <i>If YES, which one?</i>	Y N
	3. Did the difficulty arise in a situation of excessive stimulation? (Noise, bright light, etc.) <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
	4. Does your child take medication or supplements to help them fall asleep? <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
	5. Could the difficulty be associated with a medical condition? (Allergies, inflammation, sensitivity to underwear, etc.) <i>If YES, which one?</i>	Y N
	6. Does your child sleep only a few hours and wake up frequently during the night? <i>If YES, how many hours does he sleep before waking up and what causes him to wake up (teething, feeding, EM waves, etc.)?</i>	Y N
	7. Does your child have a circadian rhythm disorder (irregular sleep and wake times)? <i>If YES, which one?</i>	Y N
Environmental factors	8. Does your child have any bedtime rituals? <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
	9. Does your child have any bedtime rituals? <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
	10. Does your child fall asleep more easily when someone is present? <i>If YES, with whom?</i>	Y N
	11. Does your child take naps during the day? <i>If YES, how long does he sleep?</i>	Y N
	12. Does the bedtime ritual take more than twenty minutes (turning off all the lights, choosing three items to take to bed, etc.)? <i>If YES, how many minutes?</i>	Y N
	13. The difficulty arises in relation to certain pre-bedtime activities (use of electronic devices, drinking sugary drinks, etc.) <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
	14. Does the difficulty appear in response to (or immediately after) frustrations (punishment, sacrifices, discomfort, denial, etc.)? <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
Situational factors	15. Does the child wake up during the night? <i>If YES, how often, how long does it take, and how long does it take to fall back asleep?</i>	Y N
	16. Is difficulty an opportunity to get someone's attention? <i>If YES, whose?</i>	Y N
	17. Are parents able to get their child to sleep or back to sleep if they wake up during the night? <i>If YES, what strategies?</i>	Y N
	18. Is bedtime associated with negative experiences? <i>If YES, which ones?</i>	Y N
	19. Does your child not associate their bed with sleep? <i>If YES, what do you associate it with (arms, sofa, etc.)?</i>	Y N
	20. Does the child go to bed at different times in the evening? <i>If YES, why?</i>	Y N
	21. Is it more difficult for your child to fall asleep if they are experiencing discomfort (separation anxiety, fear of the dark, etc.)? <i>If YES, under what circumstances?</i>	Y N

Figure 1: Interview on Sleep

Intervention

Before beginning the actual intervention, the environment was organised by first creating a visual agenda for the implementation of a routine to facilitate falling asleep (soft red night light turned on in the room at least two hours beforehand; light dinner avoiding foods and drinks with high sugar and/or caffeine content: tea, hazelnut spreads, chocolate, cola, etc.; reduction of sensory stimuli; switching off all electronic devices about an hour before bedtime; relaxing activities for the child: puzzles, Lego building; colouring pictures, breathing exercises, warm bath, etc.). In addition, the same times were always maintained for both meals and bedtime [20].

Night-time sleep was encouraged by following a consistent routine that consisted of inviting the child to go to bed at a time when it was highly likely that they would fall asleep quickly (i.e. within 15 minutes of the

scheduled time). This initial bedtime was determined by calculating the average time to fall asleep during the baseline period and then adding 30 minutes (e.g., if the expected time to fall asleep was 9:00 p.m. during the baseline measurement, the initial average bedtime was set at 9:30 p.m.). The child was not allowed to go to bed or fall asleep before this time, nor to sleep beyond the scheduled wake-up time. To “normalise” this procedure, a “response cost” was introduced, which served to adjust the child’s bedtime by 30 minutes each night based on the latency of falling asleep the previous night. If the child fell asleep within 15 minutes of bedtime, bedtime would be moved forward by 30 minutes the following night. If the child did not fall asleep within 15 minutes of bedtime, bedtime would be moved back by 30 minutes the following night.

Figure 2: Number of Night-Time Awakenings for Davide: A=Baseline; B=Intervention; Follow-up=Checks after 1, 2, 3, and 4 weeks.

In addition to these initial procedures, a single-subject experimental design was used, consisting of two phases: a baseline phase (A), in which the behaviour or variable is observed before the intervention, and a treatment phase (B), in which an independent variable is introduced to assess its effect (Fig. 2). This model was used to determine the causal relationship between the intervention with the “The bedtime pass” procedure and the change in Davide’s behaviour of not waking up during the night. This procedure was implemented by following these steps:

1. A consistent routine and bedtime schedule have been established.
2. A nice card (10x8 cm) was made, decorated, coloured and laminated with the words “Pass to go to sleep” (which can be used for a simple request: another story, a hug, a glass of water, etc.; for the first three nights, the child was given two Passes to go to sleep until he understood how it worked).
3. The child was told that if he called out or got out of bed, he had to return the Pass to go to sleep. If, on the other hand, he kept it, the following morning he could exchange it for a reward of his choice (stickers to stick on, leafing through a picture book, watching a cartoon for 15 minutes or, weather permitting, going to the playground).
4. Once Davide was in bed, his parents had to leave the room and if the child called out or got up, they had to respond to his request, take him back to bed and take away his Pass.
5. If the child called out or got up after using up his Passes, his parents had to take him back to bed quietly and with minimal involvement, ignoring any other requests.

6. If Davide gave up his Pass, he could earn a bigger cumulative reward the next day.

Conclusions

The results of this study show that the Pass to go to sleep, in combination with “environmental programming” and “response cost”, led to the extinction of both resistance to bedtime and night-time awakenings. In fact, Fig. 2 shows that Davide’s night-time awakenings, which were observed during the Baseline phase (A) with related calls or exits from the room, during the intervention phase (B), were increasingly reduced until they were no longer observed, which continued during the Follow-up phase. Furthermore, calls or exits from the room never occurred during the intervention phase with greater frequency than during the initial phase [21].

In general, the reinforcers that most excited the child and worked best were when the Pass was given in the morning, as this helped Davide to “control” his behaviour in immediately satisfying a need (getting out of bed or asking for something).

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